

RESEARCH ARTICLE

3D-printed alumina-based ceramics with spatially resolved porosity

Serkan Nohut^{1,2}

¹Lithoz GmbH, Vienna, Austria

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Piri Reis University, Istanbul, Turkey

³Department of Materials Science, Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Leoben, Austria

Correspondence

Serkan Nohut, Lithoz GmbH, Mollardgasse 85a/2/64-69, Vienna 1060, Austria.
Email: snohut@lithoz.com

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Abstract

The interest on porous ceramics has increased in the last years with the developments in additive manufacturing methods, enabling design of components with complex geometries for membranes, filters, catalytic converters, or biostructures. In this study, porous alumina samples were produced by using different concentrations of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) as pore-forming agent (PFA) in a photocurable slurry via vat photopolymerization (VPP). The effect of layer thickness, PMMA particle size, and sintering temperature on the mechanical properties and microstructural features of the samples was investigated as a function of PMMA concentration. It is shown that the mechanical properties of 3D-printed porous alumina are comparable with those fabricated by conventional processes. The Young modulus, fracture toughness as well as the biaxial strength decreased with increasing weight concentration of PFA (resulting in an increased total porosity). Specially using smaller PMMA particles has a positive effect, resulting in higher Young's modulus as well as fracture toughness. The feasibility of VPP for fabricating novel parts with more complex porosity regions is explored by printing multi-material samples and porosity-graded architectures. The counterbalance effect between porosity and mechanical properties may be optimized by tailoring material composition and processing parameters.

KEYWORDS

additive manufacturing, alumina, mechanical properties, pores/porosity, Vat photopolymerization

1 | INTRODUCTION

The advantageous properties of porous ceramics, such as chemical inertness, corrosion, biocompatibility, and low density, make them superior candidates for applications that demand lightweight properties, acoustic/thermal

insulation, high thermal shock resistance, and increased capillary activity.¹ It has been reported in 2019 that, more than 16,000 scientific articles about porous ceramics have been published² in the last 20 years. In recent years, the interest and demand on porous ceramics have increased particularly in bio-based applications as porous

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ceramics may enable the impregnation of bone cells through open pores resulting in a bone growth on the biocompatible walls.³ Although there are different definitions,⁴ porous ceramics can be in general classified as macroporous, meso/microporous, and nanoporous ceramics.^{5–8} Each class of porous ceramics may be manufactured by different methods, being suitable for different applications.⁹ For example, although microporous ceramics are used in diesel particulate filters and as refractories, mesoporous ceramics are utilized in enzyme immobilization and ion exchange processes.

Porous alumina shows promising potential for different applications since it offers a high temperature stability with intermediate thermal shock resistance, very good chemical stability, and excellent biocompatibility.¹⁰ Using porous alumina is a good choice for the improvement of catalysis effectiveness which is very important for the prevention of air pollution.¹¹ Furthermore, porous alumina is a superior candidate for cost-effective membranes and filters for bioremediation, nano biosensors, and water microfiltration/nanofiltration applications.¹² For instance, the introduction of pores with sizes ranging from 1 to 10 μm into alumina sheets of multilayer ceramic membranes may improve the permeability and show good flux as well as mechanical strength.¹³ Bimodal porosity distributions, including 3D macropores and micropores, were introduced by ceramic/camphene-based 3D extrusion method and a total volumetric porosity up to 58% was observed by decreasing the initial alumina content.¹⁴ For the improvement of air bearing, a combination of design optimization and porous alumina material design has been attempted. A restrictor material composed of porous alumina ceramic membrane was manufactured by using polystyrene microspheres as pore-forming agent (PFA) and it was reported that an optimized porosity and mechanical response was achieved with a ceramic membrane of $\sim 12\%$ porosity.¹⁵

Typical conventional fabrication processes that are used in the production of porous ceramics are partial sintering, sacrificial fugitives, replica templates, direct foaming, sol-gel method, foam-gel casting, and freeze casting.¹⁶ Although conventional methods are successful in production of porous ceramics with controlled porosity and pore size distribution, they have limitations in production of complex structures with sufficient structural integrity. For example, in the replica templates, the porous ceramics have similar morphologies as those of the templates and the mechanical strength of the material may be reduced due to the pyrolysis of the template.¹⁷ An alternative has been proposed by fabricating porous ceramics via sol-gel method, however at the expense of low production efficiency.¹⁸

In recent years, the application of additive manufacturing (AM) methods has become more advantageous

for the fabrication of porous ceramic components with high dimensional accuracy. Some AM methods, such as laminated object manufacturing (LOM), vat photopolymerization (VPP), fused filament fabrication, and powder bed fusion, have been studied in literature for the manufacturing of porous ceramics.^{19,20} Most of these studies include the generation of geometric or hierarchical porous lattice structures realized by incorporating macropores in the CAD file and printing of periodic cells including regularly arranged pores.^{2,21} In practice, introduction of micropores that exist within the material is also of high interest for many applications. Therefore, in recent years, more effort has been given to combine macropores and micropores to introduce bimodal pore distribution.^{14,22} Furthermore, it has been reported that integration of traditional methods into AM may allow controlling the size distribution, orientation, and uniformity of the combination of macropores and micropores.²² The freeze-drying method has been combined with LOM for formation of porous alumina with micro level pores.²³ SiOC porous ceramics with a total porosity of $\sim 88\%$ and improved compressive strength was obtained by combining sacrificial template method and direct ink writing. In this case, poly-methylsiloxane and poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) were used in the inks as the preceramic precursor.²⁴

This article explores the fabrication of porous alumina ceramics by lithography-based ceramic manufacturing (LCM) technology. LCM is a two-stage AM method where a ceramic slurry that contains photosensitive resin is solidified through some photochemical reactions. The LCM method, developed by the company Lithoz GmbH, uses the VPP process.²⁵ LCM technology works with the principle of digital light processing (DLP) according to bottom-up approach that reduces the risk of cross-contamination during multi-material printing. A photosensitive slurry is cured via a dynamic mask through selective light exposure in the desired areas.^{26,27} As a building speed, up to 100 slices/h, meaning up to 10 mm/h can be achieved with a lateral resolution of 40 μm in the xy -direction.^{28,29} Thermal-post-processing methods, including preconditioning, debinding (removal of binder), and sintering, are applied to printed samples (so-called green body).³⁰ In LCM, no special process is applied to ceramic powders and the method ensures high dimensional precision, density, and strength with commercially available ceramic powders.

In principle, the LCM process is suitable for processing all sinterable powders, so in recent years a wide range of customer-specific materials has already been processed via the LCM route. Furthermore, with the LCM technology, ceramic components can be additively manufactured with the highest quality and precision, which differ little or not at all from conventionally manufactured ceramic

components in terms of their mechanical and material properties. By using DLP technology, entire areas can be exposed, which is a very time-effective method. In literature, it has been shown that by mixing the ceramic powder with some amounts of PFAs that will burn out and evaporate during the thermal post-processing, porous ceramics can be obtained. Adding PFAs to introduce porosity by multi-material LCM technology offers many advantages such as to set the site-specific porosity and pore size distribution without changing the printing and thermal-post-processing flow. Different PFAs have been used in previous studies for the fabrication of porous alumina,³¹ such as starch,^{32,33} polyvinyl chloride,³⁴ cellulose fibers,³⁵ phenolic resin spheres,³⁶ cotton,³⁷ nylon,³⁸ corn cob,³⁹ rice husk,⁴⁰ pre-expanded polymer microspheres,⁴¹ active yeast, lycopodium spores,⁴² and PMMA.⁴³ Porous alumina ceramics with multimodal pore size distribution have been fabricated by using pyrolyzed cellulose fibers and isotropic phenolic resin spheres with uniaxial pressing and sintering at 1700°C. It was reported that the presence of PFAs strongly affects the mechanical and thermal properties of alumina.³⁶ Different grades of porous alumina produced by using corn cob as PFA of different weight fractions and particle sizes showed that the total porosity is proportional to the PFA weight fraction and PFA particle size and the strength and hardness decrease as the PFA particle size increases.³⁹ Starch was used as a PFA in AM of porous alumina by a thermoplastic 3D printing process, which is based on the deposition of molten single droplets of PFA into the suspension. However, the maximum content of PFA for successful porous alumina production was reported as 10 vol%, due to difficulties in processing of suspension beyond this value.² Combining the starch consolidation process with the gel-casting process was attempted as an easy and low-cost process for the manufacturing of porous alumina with a total porosity up to 55.3%.⁴⁴

In this work, porous alumina samples with different porosity are fabricated with commercially available alumina slurry and PMMA powders by using the LCM method. The PMMA microbeads were selected due to their suitability for this process with respect to appropriate particle sizes and homogeneous particle distribution, for enabling the printing of specimens with rather small layer thicknesses as well as low vaporization temperature.^{45–47} PMMA particles with different sizes are used with different concentrations in this study for the formation of micropores and the effect of PMMA particle size, its concentration, sintering temperature, and layer thickness on porosity and mechanical properties of porous alumina are investigated. Young's modulus, fracture toughness as well as (biaxial) strength are determined as function of PMMA-content and total porosities. Fractographic

analyses are performed to identify fracture origins. The feasibility to include alumina (with different PMMA's) in more-complex 3D architectures is demonstrated.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Materials and sample preparation

LithaLox 350 (Lithoz GmbH), a commercially available photocurable alumina slurry containing 49% volume content of submicron α -Al₂O₃ powder, was used. As PFA, PMMA microbeads with two different particle sizes of $d_{50} = 8\text{--}11\ \mu\text{m}$ and $d_{50} = 4\text{--}7\ \mu\text{m}$ (referred as PMMA-1 and PMMA-2 respectively) were selected. The PMMA powders were mixed with LithaLox 350 slurry with a weight content of 10, 20, and 25 wt.% (named AP0, AP10, AP20, and AP25, respectively, where AP0 represents the pure LithaLox 350). The volumetric contents of PMMA powders represent 17.4%, 29.7%, and 34.5%, respectively, for samples AP10, AP20, and AP25.

The homogenous distribution of PMMA particles in the slurry plays an important role for the fabrication of homogenous monolithic ceramic parts. Therefore, the slurries and PMMA powders were centrifugally mixed at 1600 and 1750 rpm for 2 min and 1 min, respectively. The rheological behavior (i.e., dynamic viscosity) of photocurable ceramic slurry is an important factor that determines the quality of the printer components in terms of forces acting on samples during printing, wetting properties, and providing geometric details. The dynamic viscosity measurements of the slurries were conducted at room temperature using a modular compact rheometer (MCR 92) via a plate–plate arrangement. The corresponding plate diameter and gap between plates were 25 and 0.5 mm. To characterize the rheological behavior, the change of dynamic viscosity was monitored as a function of shear rate ranging from 0.1 to 1000 s⁻¹.⁴⁸

The samples were printed with a layer thickness of 25 or 50 μm using multi-material printer CeraFab Multi 2M30 developed by Lithoz GmbH.⁴⁹ The CeraFab Multi 2M30 has a lateral resolution of 35 μm . Each layer is exposed using a monochromatic (450 nm) projector with a power of 50 mW/cm² for an exposure time of 3.6 s corresponding to an energy of 180 mJ/cm². Since addition of PMMA particles did not affect the curing depth properties of the alumina slurry, same curing energy was used for all slurries. In order to capture the effect of layer thickness on total porosity and homogenous distribution of pores in the deposition direction, the processing conditions were held constant for the layer thicknesses of 25 and 50 μm . Subsequently to the printing process, the excess slurry on the samples was removed by using LithaSol 20 (Lithoz GmbH)

TABLE 1 Slurry, process parameters, and porosity of samples.

Sample	PMMA content (%)	PMMA type	Layer thickness (μm)	Sintering temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Porosity (%)
AP0-No1	0	PMMA-1	50	1650	2.2 ± 0.1
AP10-No2	10	PMMA-1	50	1650	23.4 ± 1.0
AP10-No3	10	PMMA-1	50	1550	40.1 ± 1.1
AP10-No4	10	PMMA-1	25	1650	33.2 ± 1.9
AP10-No5	10	PMMA-2	50	1650	29.7 ± 0.9
AP20-No6	20	PMMA-1	50	1650	48.9 ± 0.8
AP25-No7	25	PMMA-1	50	1650	51.3 ± 0.9

Abbreviation: PMMA, poly(methyl methacrylate).

FIGURE 1 Geometry of the alumina samples indicating the printing orientation.

and compressed air.⁴⁹ Two different sintering temperatures (i.e., 1650°C for 2 h and 1550°C for 2 h, both with a heating rate of 1 K/min) were used to investigate the effect of sintering temperature on mechanical properties and microstructure. In Table 1, the combination of samples with the slurry and process parameters as well as measured porosity values is shown.

For the materials characterization, bending bars with the dimensions of $3\text{ mm} \times 4\text{ mm} \times 50\text{ mm}$, and discs with dimensions of $D = 10\text{ mm}$ in diameter and $t = 1.0\text{ mm}$ in thickness were produced with the specified deposition direction as shown in Figure 1.

2.2 | Characterization

2.2.1 | Porosity and microstructure

During the debinding process, the PMMA particles in the slurry are decomposed and the spaces left by PMMA particles form the pores. The porosity of the samples was measured as an average of six optical images (light microscopy) using an image processing software (Stream motion) (Table 1). Prior to the measurements via light microscopy, the sample cross-sections (perpendicular to the printing direction) were polished to a $1\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ mirror finish using a Struers Tegramin-30 equipment. To observe the microstructure, the samples were thermally etched at 1450°C for 20 min. Furthermore, the surfaces were gold

coated using an Agrar Sputter Coater and scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JEOL JCM-6000Plus, Neoscope, JEOL Ltd.) images were taken before and after thermal etching. The experimental open porosity of the samples was measured by using density determination kit (SI-234A, Denver Instrument) according to EN623-2 Archimedeian method⁵⁰ where the samples were saturated in distilled water by an ultrasonic bath according to ASTM C373-088.⁵¹

2.2.2 | Young's modulus

The Young modulus of the samples was measured in ambient conditions ($\sim 23^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\sim 40\%$ relative humidity) according to EN 843-2⁵² by applying three-point bending tests on $3\text{ mm} \times 4\text{ mm} \times 50\text{ mm}$ samples with an outer span length of 40 mm in a universal testing machine (Messphysik, Microstrain, Fürstenfeld, Austria) using a load cell of 100 N. The crosshead speed and maximum load were selected as 0.5 mm/min and 35 N, respectively. From each type of sample, five tests were performed.

2.2.3 | Fracture toughness

The fracture toughness of samples was determined by using single edge V-notched beam-method according to the ISO 23146 standards.⁵³ Four-point bending tests were performed on notched specimens on a universal testing machine (Zwick 010, Zwick/Roell Ulm) using a load cell of 200 N. The tests were performed in ambient conditions ($\sim 23^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\sim 40\%$ relative humidity) by using an outer and inner span of 40 and 20 mm, respectively. The displacement speed was selected as 0.5 mm/min. A total of five specimens were tested for each sample type.

2.2.4 | Biaxial strength

For the determination of bending strength, a ball-on-three-balls testing setup was used.^{54,55} In this setup, the disc is symmetrically supported by three balls on one side and

loaded at the center of the opposite specimen side through a fourth ball.⁵⁶ The main advantage of the B3B-test is that the maximum (biaxial) stress occurs directly in the middle of the specimen and thus only a relatively small effective volume or area is loaded during testing, which minimizes the influence of edge defects. The B3B-tests were conducted on a universal testing machine (Zwick 010, Zwick/Roell Ulm) using a load cell of 10 kN, a selected displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min and an applied preload between 10 and 20 N, at ambient conditions ($\sim 23^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity of $\sim 57\%$). The samples were loaded by three supporting balls and a loading ball which had a diameter of 6.35 mm. For each sample type, 30 discs with as-printed surface condition were tested for statistical significance. In this test, the failure stress, σ_f , is taken as the maximum tensile stress that occurs at the bottom center of the specimen and it is calculated as⁵⁴

$$\sigma_f = f \left(\frac{t}{R}, \frac{R_a}{R}, \nu \right) \cdot \frac{F}{t^2} \quad (1)$$

where F is the maximum load at failure, t is the thickness of disc, R is the radius of disc, R_a is the distance between the ball contact point and the center of the disc, and ν is the Poisson ratio.⁵⁷ For monolithic materials, by assuming ν as 0.23 for alumina, the dimensionless factor f can be calculated as 1.8 for this geometry.⁵⁴

2.2.5 | Fractography

Selected fracture surfaces (broken discs) of each tested sample set were gold coated using Agrar Sputter Coater for examination. The failure origin of the broken surfaces was identified by using SEM (JEOL JCM-6000Plus, Neoscope, JEOL Ltd.).

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 | Rheological behavior

The commercially available slurries were optimized in terms of dispersing agent and additives in the organic binder and the solid content to have good flow behavior and low viscosity. As the PMMA is mixed with a slurry, the friction occurring between PMMA–PMMA and PMMA–ceramic particles as well as an increase of the solid content increase the viscosity of the slurry. Figure 2 shows the dynamic viscosities of the slurries containing different amounts of PMMA particles as a function of shear rate. The investigated alumina slurries exhibited a shear-thinning behavior. A viscosity of a slurry lower than 20 Pa s for the

FIGURE 2 Dynamic viscosities of the investigated alumina slurries.

shear rate interval from 10 to 50 s^{-1} is preferred for LCM process. Therefore, the AP0, AP10, and AP20 slurries have suitable viscosity and AP25 was used to observe the effects of high viscosity on the quality of porous alumina samples.

3.2 | Porosity and microstructure

In general, porous ceramics can be produced by either including some pore-forming additives (e.g., sponge method, direct foaming, sacrificial fugitives etc.) or partial sintering (i.e., sintering at a lower temperature). The samples that are shown in Figure 3 were all sintered at 1650°C , which is the suggested sintering temperature for LithaLox 350 to obtain dense alumina samples. Therefore, inclusion of PMMA is the main factor in the introduction of porosity in these samples.

Representative SEM images of samples (PMMA-1/ $1650^\circ\text{C}/50 \mu\text{m}$) with different PMMA weight fractions are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3A reveals the SEM image of the reference sample AP0-No1 fabricated without PMMA-content. The image indicates a rather dense sample microstructure with a low level of natural porosity, which agrees well with measured final porosity of $\sim 2.2\%$ (Table 1). The measured porosity is in good agreement with the measured relative density of about $\sim 98\%$. This value is well comparable to those of other dense 3D-printed alumina-based samples found in the literature.^{58,59} In Figure 3B, the SEM image of the sample AP10-No2 (10% PMMA) is depicted, where a rather homogeneous pore distribution with final porosity of $\sim 23\%$ within the specimen can be observed. Moreover, the average single pore size was $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$, which is similar to the particle size of PMMA-1. In contrast to this, the

FIGURE 3 SEM images of samples (poly(methyl methacrylate) [PMMA]-1/1650°C/50 μm) with different PMMA contents: (A) AP0-No1 (0% PMMA), (B) AP10-No2 (10% PMMA), (C) AP20-No6 (20% PMMA), and (D) AP25-No7 (25% PMMA). The microstructure of each sample set is shown in the yellow window.

TABLE 2 Open porosity, predicted porosity, and measured porosity of selected samples.

Sample	Open porosity (%)	Predicted porosity $V_{\text{analytical}}$ (%)	Measured porosity (%)
AP10-No2	5.9 ± 1.7	30.1	23.4 ± 1.0
AP20-No6	24.2 ± 1.1	46.3	48.9 ± 0.8
AP25-No7	25.1 ± 1.3	51.8	51.3 ± 0.9

samples with the higher PMMA-weight fractions of 20% (see Figure 3C) and 25% (see Figure 3D) indicate a favored pore distribution of about 50% along the printed interfaces. As the PMMA content increases (see Figure 3C,D), porosity and the interconnection of single pores are more pronounced. Furthermore, it is important to note that all three samples of the processing condition, PMMA-1/1650°C/50 μm , with PMMA-contents of 10%, 20%, and 25% show higher amounts of open porosity with increasing PMMA-content. This finding is in good agreement with the experimental open porosity measurements listed in Table 2. The mean grain size of the microstructure of AP10-No1 is $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$. The microstructures of AP20-No6 and AP25-No7 show similar average grain sizes of approx. $3 \mu\text{m}$ (yellow windows in Figure 3). Interestingly, the grain size of AP10-No2 with 10% PMMA seems to be larger ($\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$). PMMA is a cross-linked polymer and therefore no swelling is expected between the PMMA and the organic binder of the slurry.

The effects of other parameters such as (i) the sintering temperature, (ii) PMMA particle size, and (iii) the printing layer thickness were analyzed on samples with 10% PMMA content. SEM images of samples with fixed 10% PMMA but with different processing parameters are depicted in Figure 4. Sample AP10-No3 sintered at a lower temperature (1550°C) reveals a bimodal pore size distribution with the existence of nanopores, as can be seen in Figure 4A. As comparison, these nanopores are absent at higher sintering temperatures of 1650°C (see Figure 3B) since alumina sintered at 1650°C has a higher relative density. Furthermore, the level of porosity with a value of $\sim 40\%$ is the highest for all samples with 10% PMMA weight fraction. The sintering temperature may play an important role for the design of optimized porous samples with a higher porosity and bimodal pore size distribution. In addition, AP10-No3 shows a rather fine-grained microstructure ($\sim 2.5 \mu\text{m}$), which can be traced back to the lower selected sintering temperature of 1550°C. The sample AP10-No4 (see Figure 4B) with a selected printing layer thickness of 25 μm showed an increased content of the porosity level ($\sim 33\%$) as compared to that of AP10-No2 (see Figure 3C) with the standard layer thickness (50 μm) and a porosity of $\sim 23\%$. The mentioned difference can be explained by the fact that the pore distribution is again favored along the layer interfaces, where in samples with 25 μm printed layer thicknesses more interfaces are available (Figure S1). Furthermore, as the PMMA particles in 25 μm layer thickness can move less freely in the height direction compared to 50 μm ,

FIGURE 4 Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of fabricated with 10% poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) (AP10) using different parameters: (A) AP10-No3 (PMMA-1/1550°C/50 μm); (B) AP10-No4 (PMMA-1/1650°C/25 μm); and (C) AP10-No5 (PMMA-2/1650°C/50 μm). The yellow windows show the microstructures of the corresponding samples.

the connection between single pores occurs more frequently. Considering the microstructure of AP10-No4, the mean grain size can be estimated as $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$ (similar to AP0-No1). The samples AP10-No5 (see Figure 4C) fabricated with PMMA type 2 revealed a rather homogeneous pore size distribution compatible with the smaller powder size (5 μm) with small pores in the range of 1–2 μm . The corresponding porosity was measured as $\sim 30\%$, which is significantly higher than that of the AP10-No2-sample of PMMA-1 ($\sim 23\%$ porosity). Therefore, it can be concluded that while PMMA with a particle size of $d_{50} = 8\text{--}11 \mu\text{m}$ introduces pore size equivalent to its size, the pores get smaller during the thermal processing when smaller PMMA particles with $d_{50} = 4\text{--}7 \mu\text{m}$ are used. As a result, a desired bimodal pore size distribution can be obtained by combining PMMA particles of different sizes. Furthermore, the smaller used particle size of PMMA-2 may affect the final microstructure, yielding to slightly smaller grains ($\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$).

The ceramic slurry is a combination of the ceramic powder, and the organic part, which is composed of monomers, photo initiators, and other additives. As the porosity is the volume content of pores or free spaces with respect to the total solid volume of the material, $V_{\text{analytical}}$ can be used for the analytical prediction of the porosity (Equation 2).

$$V_{\text{analytical}} = \frac{V_p}{V_c + V_p} \quad (2)$$

where V_p is the volume of PMMA and V_c is the volume of ceramic powder in the mixed slurry. The analytically predicted porosities are compared with the determined porosities in Table 2 and they are in good agreement with each other.

3.3 | Young's modulus

Figure 5A,B shows the Young modulus of the samples as a function of the PMMA weight fraction and measured porosity, respectively. In general, increasing the PMMA content leads to an increase in the resulting porosity level. The E-modulus decreases with increasing PMMA-content and porosity, as it can be clearly seen on sample sets AP0-No1 and AP25-No7 (PMMA-1/1650°C/50 μm). The Young modulus of AP10-No2 of $237 \pm 2 \text{ GPa}$ is about 33% lower than that of the pure alumina reference material AP0-No1 ($352 \pm 9 \text{ GPa}$). The Young modulus of pure alumina with its porosity of $\sim 2\%$ is in good agreement with the values stated in the literature.⁶⁰ The samples with 20% (AP20-No6) and 25% PMMA (AP25-No7) content show measured Young's moduli of $173 \pm 12 \text{ GPa}$ and $155 \pm 8 \text{ GPa}$, which are 51% and 56% lower than that of AP0-No1. The decreasing trend of the Young modulus with rising porosity level fits well with the observations in the study executed by Asmani et al.,⁶¹ where Young's modulus measured by ultrasonic

FIGURE 5 Young's modulus as a function of (A) poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) content and (B) final porosity.

velocities decreased by increasing the volume fraction of porosity.

In the case of alumina with 10% PMMA printed with thinner layers of 25 μm (AP10-No4), the Young modulus was 228 ± 12 GPa, which is slightly below to that of AP10-No2 with standard thickness (50 μm) due to a higher porosity. Therefore, the layer thickness does not have a big effect on Young's modulus. Furthermore, with the same selected PMMA-content but with lower sintering temperature (AP10-No3) the Young modulus (159 ± 3 GPa) drastically decreases with a difference of $\sim 30\%$. This finding can be traced back to the higher porosity of $\sim 40\%$ (AP10-No3) as compared to that of $\sim 23\%$ (AP10-No2). However, selecting the fine PMMA-particle size of 5 μm (PMMA-2) has a positive effect on the Young moduli of porous 3D-printed alumina: The Young modulus of AP10-No5 (PMMA-2/1650°C/50 μm) was 287 ± 8 GPa, which is $\sim 20\%$ higher than that of AP10-No2 (PMMA-2/1650°C/50 μm) (237 ± 2 GPa) for the same level of PMMA content (10%). This is because the average single pore size decreases from about 10 μm to the range of 1–2 μm .

3.4 | Fracture toughness

Figure 6A,B shows the measured fracture toughness, K_{IC} , of 3D-printed alumina as a function of the PMMA weight fraction and the porosity level, respectively. The individual values are reported in Table 3. The fracture toughness of the relatively dense pure alumina (AP0-No1) was 2.86 ± 0.07 MPa $\text{m}^{1/2}$, similar to the K_{IC} of 3D-printed alumina reported in literature.⁶² The K_{IC} of alumina samples AP0-No1 to AP25-No7, with the same PMMA particle types, sintering temperature, and layer thickness (i.e., PMMA-1/1650°C/50 μm) follows a decreasing trend with increasing PMMA-content and corresponding porosity. These experimental results are in good agreement

with the fracture toughness of porous ceramics fabricated with conventional methods, as reported in literature, where the fracture toughness of alumina may decrease by approximately 40% and 55% for 20% and 28% porosity, respectively.^{63,64}

The fracture toughness of alumina sample AP10-No2 was $K_{\text{IC}} = 1.96 \pm 0.13$ MPa $\text{m}^{1/2}$, which is approximately 30% lower than that of pure alumina. In the case of 3D-printed alumina fabricated with higher PMMA content, such as 20% and 25%, K_{IC} decreased to 1.44 ± 0.02 and 1.37 ± 0.10 MPa $\text{m}^{1/2}$, respectively. The corresponding porosity levels of $\sim 50\%$ of those samples yield to a drop of K_{IC} of about 50% of the value of nonporous alumina. The fracture toughness of AP10-No4 samples (with 10% PMMA), fabricated with thinner layers (25 μm), was $K_{\text{IC}} = 2.05 \pm 0.08$ MPa $\text{m}^{1/2}$ on the same level as the AP10-No2 samples ($K_{\text{IC}} = 1.96 \pm 0.13$ MPa $\text{m}^{1/2}$) with the same PMMA content, yet designed with thicker layers (50 μm). This finding indicates no significant influence of the printed layer thickness on the fracture toughness of alumina, even when the porosity is slightly higher (see Figure 6B). The sintering temperature significantly affects the fracture toughness, as can be seen by comparing sample AP10-No3 sintered at 1550°C (i.e., $K_{\text{IC}} = 1.49 \pm 0.04$ MPa $\text{m}^{1/2}$) with sample AP10-No2 sintered at 1650°C (i.e., $K_{\text{IC}} = 1.96 \pm 0.13$ MPa $\text{m}^{1/2}$), as may be expected. Interestingly, the size of the PMMA particles affects the fracture toughness: Sample AP10-No5 (with 4–7 μm PMMA particles) has a $\sim 15\%$ higher K_{IC} (i.e., $K_{\text{IC}} = 2.27 \pm 0.13$ MPa $\text{m}^{1/2}$) than sample AP10-No2 (with 8–11 μm PMMA particles).

3.5 | Strength distributions

In Figure 7, the failure probability (P_f) is plotted versus failure stress (σ_f) for samples with different porosity grades and/or processing parameters (AP0-No1 to AP25-No7) in

FIGURE 6 Fracture toughness as a function of (A) poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) content and (B) final porosity.

TABLE 3 Characteristic strength as well as Weibull modulus 90% confidence intervals.

Sample	Fracture toughness, K_{Ic} (MPa m ^{1/2})	Characteristic strength, σ_0 (MPa)	Weibull modulus, m (-)	Characteristic critical defect size, $a_{0,c}$ (μ m)
AP0-No1	2.86 ± 0.07	454 [444–464]	15 [12–19]	10
AP10-No2	1.96 ± 0.13	238 [234–242]	21 [16–26]	17
AP10-No3	1.49 ± 0.04	212 [210–215]	31 [23–37]	13
AP10-No4	2.05 ± 0.08	212 [210–214]	30 [22–36]	24
AP10-No5	2.27 ± 0.13	234 [228–239]	14 [11–17]	24
AP20-No6	1.44 ± 0.02	144 [141–148]	15 [11–18]	25
AP25-No7	1.37 ± 0.10	124 [122–126]	21 [16–25]	31

FIGURE 7 (A and B) Strength distributions of alumina samples with different porosity grades. The reader is cautioned that the symbols of AP10-No3 and AP10-No4 in (B) are overlapping.

a Weibull diagram. The straight lines represent the best fit of the strength data according to maximum likelihood method.

The characteristic strength (σ_0) and Weibull modulus (m) with 90% confidence intervals were calculated according to EN-843-5 standards^{65–67} and are listed in Table 3. The

FIGURE 8 Weibull modulus plotted versus characteristic strength of 3D-printed alumina with different poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) contents.

Weibull modulus is a measure of scatter of the strength data and characteristic strength shows the stress value at which 63% of all samples fail. The characteristic critical size defect represents the size of the defect that causes the failure.⁶⁸

For the sake of comparison, m is plotted over σ_0 for all tested samples in Figure 8.

For the samples with the same processing conditions (PMMA-1/1650°C/50 μm), a clear effect of the PMMA-content on the characteristic strength can be seen in Figure 8. The characteristic strength (σ_0) decreases significantly with increasing PMMA fraction (see Figure 9A), which may be traced back to the final pore size distributions after burning out.

For instance, sample AP10-No2 (with only 10%wt. PMMA) has a strength ca. 50% lower than the reference sample AP0-No1 (without PMMA), that is, $\sigma_0 \sim 240$ MPa versus $\sigma_0 \sim 450$ MPa. The relative difference of the characteristic strength of samples with PMMA-weight fraction of 10% and 20% is approx. 65%, that is, ($\sigma_0 \sim 240$ MPa vs. $\sigma_0 \sim 145$ MPa). An additional 5% increase of the PMMA-weight fraction (AP25-No7) decreases the strength to $\sigma_0 \sim 125$ MPa. In summary, a 25% PMMA content (i.e., ca. 50% porosity) can reduce the strength almost four times as compared to dense alumina (see Figure 9B). This finding may be explained by considering the final intensity of pores listed in Table 1, showing increasing pore content from $\sim 2\%$ (AP0) to more than 50% (AP25). The decrease of the strength with increasing amount of porosity has been observed on different alumina-based materials in other works.^{69,70} Especially, the pore size distribution can be considered a significant indicator for failure analysis as will be described in the following part.

However, all sample sets of the condition (PMMA-1/1650°C/50 μm) show a rather high Weibull modulus (15–21) without significant differences in terms of Weibull statistics, which indicates similar width of the strength distributions. The Weibull moduli of all samples are well comparable with that of dense 3D-printed alumina as reported in a previous work.⁷¹ This experimental finding shows that increasing pore content may not have a significant effect on the reliability of 3D-printed alumina.

For the samples fabricated with 10% PMMA using different parameters as well as PMMA-type, the characteristic strength is slightly different, as may be seen in Figures 7 and 8. The characteristic strength of AP10-No2 (PMMA-1/1650°C/50 μm) is $\sim 15\%$ higher than those of AP10-No3 (PMMA-1/1550°C/50 μm) and AP10-No4 (PMMA-1/1650°C/25 μm), indicating only a small effect of sintering temperature and/or printed layer thickness (~ 240 vs. ~ 210 MPa). The PMMA type does not significantly influence the characteristic strength, as may be realized by comparing the characteristic strength of AP10-No2 (PMMA-1) with that of AP10-No5 (PMMA-2) (Table 3). However, the Weibull moduli for all sample sets are rather high. The Weibull modulus of AP10-No3 sintered at lower temperature (1550°C) shows a value of $m \sim 31$ and is significantly higher ($\sim 50\%$) than that of AP10-No2 (1650°C) with $m \sim 21$. The same trend was observed for the sample AP10-No4 printed with smaller layer thickness (25 μm) with $m \sim 30$. The Weibull modulus in sample AP10-No5 with PMMA-2 ($m \sim 14$) is lower than that of AP10-No2 ($m \sim 21$), which was fabricated with the same conditions but with PMMA-1 particles. The reason for a relatively high Weibull modulus for the porous samples with large PMMA particles, compared to the dense samples or porous with smaller PMMA particles, may be associated with the role of the pore in initiating the fracture. Large pores seem to act as fracture origins, whereas small pores may not always be the fracture origin. A fractographic analysis is reported below to validate this hypothesis.

3.6 | Fractographic analysis

SEM images of typical failure origins found in representative fracture surfaces of each sample set are shown in Figure 10. In most cases, surface or near-surface networks of pores were responsible for failure in 3D-printed porous alumina. To quantify the observations, the critical defect size, a_c , that causes failure, has been calculated by using the Griffith criterion⁷² according to linear elastic fracture mechanics, as follows:

FIGURE 9 Characteristic strength as a function of (A) poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) content and (B) final porosity.

$$a_c = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\frac{K_{IC}}{Y\sigma_f} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

where σ_f is the failure stress, K_{IC} is the fracture toughness, and Y is the geometric factor. In this regard, Y depends on the loading configuration as well as shape of the considered defects. It is worth noting that for the estimation of the critical defect size, a_c , the characteristic strength (σ_0) and the average fracture toughness K_{IC} (Table 3) for each sample set with different porosity grade have been taken, respectively. As most of the samples fractured from defects located on the surface (or subsurface), Y has been set as 1.12, as typical for semielliptical surface flaws.^{72,73} The characteristic critical defect sizes, $a_{0,c}$, for samples AP0-No1 to AP25-No7, are listed in Table 3.

Figure 10A shows the typical fracture surface of the dense alumina sample AP0-No1. Only large surface or subsurface grains were identified as failure origins. The estimated critical defect size of $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ (Table 3) is of the order of magnitude of large grains (or an accumulation of large grains) directly located at the tensile side within the failure region. Figure 10B shows a typical defect found in the specimen of sample set AP10-No2 (10% PMMA). A network of pores (open porosity) located near to the surface region was responsible for failure. In Figure 10C a surface artifact responsible for failure was identified on the fracture surface of AP10-No3 (10% PMMA) sintered at lower temperature of 1550 $^{\circ}$ C. Especially the presence of more rounded and uniform pore structures acting as critical defects (at higher fracture stresses) may be responsible for the relatively high Weibull modulus measured (i.e., $m \sim 31$). The same statement holds for the sample set AP10-No4 ($m \sim 30$) fabricated with 25 μm layer thickness, where a uniform network of uniform pores was identified at the fracture region (see Figure 10D). Although the smaller particle size of PMMA-type 2 (AP10-No5) yields

rather uniform pore size distribution (see Figure 10E), near-surface artifacts of different sizes caused by the printing process may be responsible for the lower $m = 14$. Likewise, the m of 15 of the sample of AP20-No6 (20% PMMA) could be explained by the higher amount of open porosity, as seen in Figure 10F, and the presence of printing artifacts on top layers (only in few cases). Regarding sample AP25-No7, with the highest porosity level of $\sim 50\%$, the combination of surface artifacts (network of pores) together with the uniform pore size distribution (see Figure 10G) may explain the relatively moderate scatter in strength and thus higher Weibull modulus (i.e., $m \sim 21$).

4 | TOWARD 3D-PRINTED DESIGNS WITH SPATIALLY RESOLVED POROSITY

The newly developed LCM multi-material printer CeraFab Multi 2M30 specifically enables introduction of complex gradients of porosity in the microstructure in a single process. The printer offers two approaches for multi-material printing.⁴⁸ In the layer-by-layer approach, each individual layer can be printed by any of two materials. With this approach, the multilayered and sandwich structures can be printed. In the within-layer approach, two materials can be used together in each layer, which enables the realization of functionally graded ceramics. As a result, it is possible to introduce a material change both parallel and perpendicular to the deposition direction. To highlight the feasibility of 3D-printing of complex porous architectures containing different PMMA-contents (AP0-No1 and AP20-No6), two examples of possible demonstrators are given in the following.

- (i) Figure 11 shows a multi-material sample composed of an outer dense cylinder with a porous lattice inner

FIGURE 10 Representative surface (or subsurface) defects of samples: (A) AP0-No1, (B) AP10-No2, (C) AP10-No3, (D) AP10-No4, (E) AP10-No5, (F) AP20-No6, and (G) AP25-No7, respectively. The larger grains in (a) are indicated by yellow arrows. The observed networks of pores that may be responsible for failure (B–G) are indicated by yellow dashed lines.

structure. Having varying porosities between an outer shell and an inner lattice structure has a promising potential to be used in bone replacements. The samples were immersed into dye penetration agent that penetrates pores and makes the porous regions red. It has been observed that a minimum wall thickness of $200\ \mu\text{m}$ could be produced without inducing cracks in the component.

(ii) Figure 12A,B illustrates a 3D-printed cube with spatially resolved (gradient) porosity in radial, vertical, horizontal, and diagonal directions. In Figure 12C, some layer pictures are represented to show the change of cured pixels in the deposition direction, proving gradient of material and thus material properties, as determined in previous section on bulk porous alumina parts. This sample was fabricated in

FIGURE 11 Multi-material sample composing of outer dense cylinder (white) and inner porous lattice structures (red).

cooperation with Fraunhofer Institute for Computer Graphics Research IGD. The pixel-based layer images were prepared with the software GraMMaCAD that was developed by Fraunhofer Institute for Computer Graphics Research IGD, Darmstadt, Germany, which enables addition of smooth gradient of material to traditional CAD models.

These two demonstrators show the capabilities of the LCM-printing process for complex architectures combining dense and porous lattice structures or porosity-graded architectures, which may enable the fabrication of components with spatially resolved properties.

5 | CONCLUSION

In this article, porous alumina samples were produced by combining PMMA as sacrificial PFA with LCM technology to investigate the effect of PMMA content on porosity, microstructure, and mechanical properties. The effect of PMMA particle size, sintering temperature, and layer thickness during the printing process on the mechanical properties was investigated. The main conclusions of this study can be summarized as follows:

- Inclusion of PMMA articles increases the viscosity of the slurry since the content of organic binder decreases as the PMMA content increases. As there is a maximum limit of viscosity of slurry so that it can be used in LCM technology successfully, the solid content of the slurry should be lower than ~49 vol.% to achieve PMMA contents higher than 25%.
- An increased amount of PMMA resulted in a higher total porosity as well as open porosity. The PMMA particles form the pores, which have a shape and dimension close to the used PMMA particles and are homogeneously distributed. As the amount of PMMA particles increases, the pores start to interact with each other and create networks that result in an increase in open porosity.
- The fracture toughness, Young's modulus, and characteristic strength of the samples decreased with the

FIGURE 12 Images of the sintered porosity graded cube produced in a multi-material printer by using AP0-No1 and AP20-No6 slurries: (A) porosity-graded alumina samples and porosity-graded cube that have various gradient architectures on each side; (B) the corresponding single side views of the cube; (C) change of pixel-based layer images in printing direction to achieve gradient.

porosity content. The use of smaller PMMA particles resulted in slightly higher Young's modulus and fracture toughness, even at levels of 30% porosity.

- Sintering ceramics at lower temperatures cause additional porosity due to partial sintering. Decreasing the sintering temperature from 1650 to 1550°C was shown to have a negative effect both in toughness and strength, associated with a bimodal pore size distribution that was observed for these conditions.
- The layer thickness had almost no effect on the mechanical properties, which gives more flexibility for the design of multilayered architectures containing layers with different porosity and/or ceramic materials. It is worth noting that the characterized mechanical properties of 3D-printed porous alumina are well comparable with those manufactured by conventional processes.

Two demonstrator parts were printed to show the capabilities of the LCM-printing process for complex architectures combining dense and porous lattice structures (multi-material sample) or porous graded architectures (cube). It has been demonstrated that both examples are feasible by using the two-vat multi-material printing system with PMMA, which may open new opportunities for designing more complex systems in future applications.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Serkan Nohut manufactured the samples, Josef Schlacher designed and performed the experiments. Serkan Nohut and Josef Schlacher contributed equally to the article. Irina Kraveva carried out the porosity and microstructure analyses. The discussion and evaluation of the results and preparation of the manuscript were performed by all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the article.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered potential competing interests: Martin Schwentenwein is an employee of Lithoz GmbH, a manufacturer, and a supplier of the used CeraFab 3D printer. The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

ORCID

Serkan Nohut <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6577-5489>

Martin Schwentenwein <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2076-5575>

Raul Bermejo <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6891-3653>

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